

Linking specific energy input to microstructure and rheology in microfluidized citrus fibre cellulose microfibril dispersions

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to establish a quantitative link between specific energy input during microfluidization and the resulting microstructure and rheology of citrus-fibre-derived cellulose microfibril dispersions. Dispersions containing 0.5 wt%, 1.0 wt% and 1.5 wt% citrus fibre were microfluidized across a range of processing intensities, after which their network structure was visualized by confocal laser scanning microscopy and their viscoelastic behaviour was evaluated by oscillatory rheology. Specific energy input, expressed as the pressure derived energy supplied per unit mass of fibre, was introduced as a processing parameter and was found to govern both microstructure and rheology. Confocal laser scanning microscopy revealed a heterogeneous network composed of flocs of cellulose microfibrils, separated by microfibril-poor void regions forming the continuous phase. Increasing the specific energy input reorganized this architecture, altering both the floc volume fraction and the spatial homogeneity of the network. The storage modulus G' showed a clear non-monotonic dependence on specific energy input, with moderate inputs strengthening the network and higher inputs reducing its elasticity. Across all concentrations, G' scaled with bulk fibre concentration according to a power law, while the scaling of the floc elasticity with the microfibril concentration inside the flocs remained constant. Using the invariant intra-floc exponent to scale G' by the bulk fibre concentration collapsed all measurements onto a single master curve governed by specific energy input. This collapse reveals two regimes separated by a threshold, establishing a quantitative processing–structure–property framework for microfluidized citrus-fibre networks.

1. Introduction

The rising demand for sustainable resources and clean-label formulations has intensified the interest in renewable biopolymers (Asioli et al., 2017; Drishya et al., 2025). Among these, lignocellulosic materials derived from plant biomass stand out as highly abundant, biodegradable and cost-effective (Jiju et al., 2025). Cellulose, the most prevalent biopolymer and main constituent of plant cell walls (Ye et al., 2020), consists of linear chains of β -(1,4) linked D-glucose molecules that aggregate into cellulose microfibrils (CMFs) (Jakob et al., 2022). CMFs typically measure 3–4 nm in diameter (Kennedy et al., 2007) and associate into larger fibril bundles of 10–25 nm in diameter due to van der Waals interaction and hydrogen bonding (Gibson, 2012; Ohshima, 2014; Song et al., 2020; Veen et al., 2014). The hierarchical structure

imparts insolubility and rigidity (Martínez-Sanz et al., 2015). When dispersed into microfibrils, the material exhibits high aspect ratios, large surface areas and strong interparticle interactions, enabling the formation of space-spanning networks (Jarvis, 2023; Liimatainen et al., 2011; Mohan et al., 2017; Xu et al., 2013). Such properties underpin applications in coatings (Grüneberger et al., 2014), edible films (Valencia et al., 2019) and packaging (Spence et al., 2010) but also in foods where CMFs can be used as texture modifiers (Blok et al., 2021; Serpa et al., 2016; Ström et al., 2013), as fat replacer (Blok et al., 2023), and as stabilizer for emulsions and foams (Bai et al., 2021; Nomena et al., 2018). While wood pulp or cotton are common sources of cellulosic material, alternative feedstocks are gaining attention to reduce reliance on forestry resources (Pennells et al., 2020). Citrus fibre, a byproduct of juice processing, and pectin extraction, is particularly promising as it

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rich in primary cell wall material in which the fundamental structural units are cellulose microfibrils (CMFs) together with associated polysaccharides such as hemicellulose and residual pectin. In their native state, in primary cell walls, these microfibrils are embedded within a composite matrix of hemicellulose and pectin, which interact with the cellulose surface through hydrogen bonding, electrostatic interactions, and occasionally covalent linkages, thereby contributing to the cohesive and tightly integrated architecture of the cell wall (Broxterman & Schols, 2018).

Realizing the advanced functionalities of CMFs hinges upon controlling their dispersion state and the resulting three-dimensional network structure (Mohan et al., 2017; Veen et al., 2015). Among various processing methods, ultra-high shear processing methods, such as high-pressure homogenization (HPH) and microfluidization have emerged as promising methods to overcome the attractive forces within cellulose aggregates (Djafari Petroudy et al., 2021). The intense shear during the process, promotes the delamination of the aggregates, and disintegration into microfibrils and microfibril bundles.

The influence of ultra high shear processing on the microstructure and functionality has been studied extensively on well-defined cellulosic systems such as bacterial cellulose or wood pulp derived materials (Mohan et al., 2018; Taheri & Samyn, 2016; Veen et al., 2015; Yang & Berglund, 2021). For these materials, concentration dependent scaling of the storage modulus G' is well established which provides direct insight into network architecture and interparticle interactions. In contrast, primary cell wall materials such as citrus fibre are gaining interest, yet the influence of processing on the functionality remains underexplored (Bruno et al., 2021; Morales-Medina et al., 2020; Serial et al., 2021; Su et al., 2021). Their composite nature, comprising both fibrillar cellulose and substantial soluble polysaccharide fractions, leads to distinct and more complex responses under ultra-high shear. Intense mechanical treatment can induce depolymerization and solubilization of residual pectin, suggesting that both insoluble and soluble matrix components reorganize due to microfluidization (Chen et al., 2012; Tu et al., 2014; Yu et al., 2021).

However, studies on ultra-high-shear treatment of primary cell-wall materials remain mostly qualitative and lack a quantitative framework connecting processing conditions to network architecture and mechanical properties, limiting the ability to fully exploit the functional potential of this promising material. Establishing this framework requires a parameter that captures how processing conditions influence microstructure and functionality (Morales-Medina et al., 2020). Yet, processing intensity is usually characterised by pressure and number of passes, which can be insufficient when different combinations of these conditions lead to comparable microstructures or when samples of varying concentration are evaluated (Morales-Medina et al., 2020; Taheri & Samyn, 2016).

Quantifying microstructure is essential for understanding how processing intensity governs the network architecture and rheology of CMF systems. Although most studies remain qualitative, mesoscale descriptors such as floc area fraction effectively relate microstructural changes emerging from microfluidization processing to rheology (Veen et al., 2015). The concentration-dependent scaling of the storage modulus, well established for purified cellulose microfibrils, provides a powerful framework to assess the network properties. (Hill, 2008; Mohan et al., 2018; Pääkkö et al., 2007; Veen et al., 2015). However, the concentration dependence of G' has hardly been discussed in microfluidized CMF networks derived from primary cell wall materials.

The present study aims to systematically investigate and quantify the effect how processing conditions during microfluidization of primary cell wall material impacts the microstructure and alter their mechanical response. The specific energy input is introduced as a key parameter governing these microstructural and rheological changes. Confocal microscopy combined with image analysis is used to quantify structural reorganization induced by processing. Oscillatory rheology assesses elasticity and reveals concentration-dependent scaling of the storage

modulus (G'). By integrating structural and mechanical metrics, this work advances understanding of processing–microstructure–elasticity relationships in CMF systems derived from primary cell walls and supports the rational design of clean-label formulations with controlled texture.

2. Methods and materials

2.1. Materials

The samples were prepared by dispersing citrus fibre (CF, supplier batch number: 1.P48940) Herbacel AQ + type N from Herbafood Ingredients GmbH, Germany (65.8 wt% cellulose from primary plant cell walls, 3.7 wt% hemicellulose, ~16.5 wt% pectin and 5.3 wt% of proteinaceous materials (Fechner et al., 2013; Qi et al., 2021)) in demineralised water. Calcoflour White, obtained from Sigma Aldrich was used as fluorescent dye for the Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy.

2.2. Sample preparation

The dispersions were prepared by dispersing 0.5 wt%, 1.0 wt% and 1.5 wt% of citrus fibre in demineralised water. This concentration range was selected as these dispersions could be reliably processed employing the lab scale microfluidizer used in this study. The mixture was gently stirred using a magnetic stirring bar to facilitate initial dispersion and hydration of the fibres. After 10 min of stirring using the magnetic stirring bar, the sample (800 ml) was subjected to high shear mixing using a Silverson mixer at 3000 rpm for 5 min. Afterwards, the dispersion was passed once through a Microfluidizer M110 S (Microfluidics, USA), with a z-shaped (G-10Z) diamond coated interaction chamber with a diameter of 87 μm . For the microfluidization process various operational pressures P ranging from 200 to 1200 bar were applied. For this, preliminary tests were performed to identify the operational pressure range. Operational pressures below 200 bar for 0.5 wt% dispersions and below 500 bar for 1.0 wt% and 1.5 wt% dispersions led to clogging of the 87 μm interaction chamber. These observations identified the minimum operational pressure used in this study, while 1200 bar corresponds to highest pressure the used system could reliably maintain.

The processing intensity during the microfluidization step has been quantified by calculating the specific energy input E_{spec} for each microfluidization pressure and fibre concentration. The specific energy input represents the pressure-derived energy supplied per unit mass of fibre during microfluidization and was obtained using Eq. (1):

$$E_{\text{spec}} = \frac{P}{c_{\text{fibre}}}, \quad (1)$$

where P is the operational pressure applied during the microfluidization process and c_{fibre} is the fibre mass concentration of the dispersions. The fibre concentration tested were converted to mass concentration assuming a density of the dispersion of $\approx 1000 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. The resulting values of E_{spec} are expressed as kJ g^{-1} .

To quantify the rheological properties of the continuous phase, the supernatant of the microfluidized 0.5 wt% Citrus Fibre dispersions was isolated by centrifugation. The samples were centrifuged for 2 h at a speed of 4000 rpm at a temperature of 20 °C, after which the clear supernatant was collected without disturbing the sedimented flocs.

2.3. Rheology

The rheological measurements were performed on a Physica MCR 301 Rheometer (Anton Paar, Austria) equipped with a sandblasted 50 mm parallel plate. Roughly 2.5 mL of the sample was carefully loaded using a spoon. The geometry then was lowered to “trimming-position” to get a gap size of 1.025 mm. This position of the geometry allowed for trimming the excessive sample. After trimming, the geometry was

lowered to get a final gap size of 1.00 mm. Temperature control during measurements was maintained at 25 °C using a water bath (Viscotherm VT2, Switzerland) in combination with a Peltier system. The rheological response of the sample was measured when subjected to a constant strain of 0.1% and a constant angular frequency of 1 Hz for 5 min. A shear strain amplitude of 0.1% was chosen for the frequency sweeps, as this value is widely used for cellulose-based fibrillar dispersions and was confirmed to lie well within the linear viscoelastic region (LVR) (Mohan et al., 2018; Morales-Medina et al., 2020; Nomena et al., 2021; Veen et al., 2015). This was done to equilibrate the sample and to observe the restructuring of the sample after it was loaded onto the rheometer and the geometry was lowered. Amplitude sweeps were conducted to determine the viscoelastic regime and the critical yield stress. The amplitudes applied ranged from 0.1 to 300 % strain, and the angular frequency was kept constant at 1 Hz. To capture the frequency-dependent behavior of the dispersions, frequency sweeps were performed immediately following the amplitude sweep. For this, the angular frequency was gradually increased from 1 rad/s to 225 rad/s while the shear strain was kept constant at 0.1%. All rheological measurements were performed in triplicate. For evaluating the trends of G' against the specific energy input, G' was calculated as the mean over the final 60 s of the time sweep, and error bars in all figures represent the standard deviation. Differences in G' across specific energy inputs/operational pressures were assessed separately for each fibre concentration using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post-hoc test ($\alpha = 0.05$). For scaling relationships (e.g., Fig. 5), linear regression was used to obtain the slope, standard error, and 95% confidence interval (CI), together with Pearson's r and R^2 . As the scaling exponent n is obtained as fitted parameter with one value per operational pressure, we report its standard error and 95% CI.

Floor curves of the continuous phase were performed on a Physica MCR 301 Rheometer (Anton Paar, Austria) equipped with a sandblasted 50 mm parallel plate. The sample was loaded by lowering the geometry to get a gap size of 1.00 mm while rotating at low angular velocity to facilitate uniform spreading. Approximately 2.5 ml of the supernatant was loaded onto the plate using a pipette. Once the surface was uniformly covered, the rotation was stopped and the sample was allowed to equilibrate for 2 min before measurement. The viscosity of the supernatant was measured using a shear-rate sweep at 25 °C, and the value at 10 s^{-1} was used for comparison.

2.4. Confocal scanning laser microscopy (CSLM)

Images of the microstructure were taken using a confocal microscope (Zeiss LSM 880, Germany), using both a 20x and 63x magnification objective. The samples were dyed using by adding an aliquot of Calcofluor white solution (1 wt% in water). The samples were measured around 14 h after addition of the staining solution to ensure a homogeneous distribution of the dye throughout the sample. For the measurement, a drop of the stained sample was placed on a microscope glass slide and topped with a cover slide to prevent evaporation of and drying of the sample. For all images the contrast was inverted for clarity purposes. White regions present the absence of fibre while darker regions are showing cellulose fibres.

2.5. Image analysis and processing

For analysis and quantification of the microstructure ImageJ 1.54p was used. Images were processed by first adjusting the contrast by employing the "Enhance contrast" function of ImageJ and setting the value to 0.4% saturated pixel and normalizing the histogram to stretch values linearly to fill the full range of the histogram. Afterwards the images were converted to 8-bit. For each sample, a 7x7 tile scan (49 images) was acquired. These 49 fields of view are spatially adjacent and were collected within a region identified as representative after scanning the sample using the live view mode of the microscope. Each image

was analysed individually, and the structural parameters were calculated per micrograph. The mean value across all 49 images is reported and the standard deviation across the tile scans is used as the statistical error and plotted as error bar.

The network homogeneity parameter (NHP) is calculated following (Veen et al., 2015). The NHP can be obtained by calculating the full width half maximum of the fluorescence intensity distribution of the confocal image and dividing by 256 to yield a number between zero and one.

To obtain the area fraction of flocs (AF_{floc}) the images were segmented into foreground and background parts by employing the automatic threshold function employing the "IsoData" algorithm in ImageJ (Ridler & Calvard, 1978). The "IsoData" function uses an iterative algorithm to separate foreground and background. It calculates the average of pixel intensities above and below a starting threshold and repeatedly updates this value until convergence, producing a binary segmentation based on intensity distribution.

For quantification of the area of flocs and voids the "Analyse particles" function in ImageJ was employed. To obtain the area fraction of flocs the area of each of the flocs A_{floc} was summed up for each image to get the total area the flocs are occupying $A_{\text{floc,tot}}$. AF_{floc} is then calculated by dividing $A_{\text{floc,tot}}$ by the total area of the image A_{tot} : $AF_{\text{floc}} = A_{\text{floc,tot}}/A_{\text{tot}}$. Because the microstructure is assumed to be isotropic, the 2D area fraction is used as a stereological approximation of the 3D floc volume fraction $AF_{\text{floc}} \approx \phi_{\text{floc}}$ (Weibel & Elias, 1967). This apparent floc volume fraction ϕ_{floc} is subsequently used in the structural analysis and scaling relations.

2.6. Model for relating bulk and floc elastic moduli

To analyse how floc and void fractions contribute to the macroscopic elasticity, the system was treated as a two-phase composite consisting of fibre-rich regions (flocs) and fibre-free regions (voids). The elastic response of each phase can be modelled by using the Reuss-Voigt-Hill averaging scheme, which has been widely applied to heterogeneous composite materials, such as fibre-reinforced and fibrillar networks (Chatterjee, 2011; Hill, 1952; Reuss, 1929; Veen et al., 2015; Voigt, 1889). Under this framework, the bulk storage modulus G'_{bulk} of a two-phase composite composed of floc and voids with the volume fraction of flocs ϕ_{floc} and of voids ϕ_{void} is bounded by the Voigt bound (Eq. (2)):

$$G'_{\text{Voigt}} = \phi_{\text{floc}} G'_{\text{floc}} + \phi_{\text{void}} G'_{\text{void}} \quad (2)$$

and the Reuss bound (Eq. (3)):

$$G'_{\text{Reuss}} = \left(\frac{\phi_{\text{floc}}}{G'_{\text{floc}}} + \frac{\phi_{\text{void}}}{G'_{\text{void}}} \right)^{-1} \quad (3)$$

The Reuss-Voigt-Hill scheme represents the arithmetic mean of the bounds: $G'_{\text{Bulk}} = (G'_{\text{Voigt}} + G'_{\text{Reuss}})/2$

Assuming that the void phase does not sustain elastic load and thus $G'_{\text{void}} = 0$, this simplifies to Eq. (4):

$$G'_{\text{bulk}} = \phi_{\text{floc}} G'_{\text{floc}} \quad (4)$$

This simplified form is used to estimate the storage modulus of the flocs G'_{floc} from the measured G'_{bulk} , using the floc volume fraction derived from CSLM.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Microstructural characterization

Microfluidization markedly alters the microstructure of citrus fibre dispersions by applying ultra-high shear stresses that disrupt aggregated

cellulose structures and promote deagglomeration of CMFs (Kuijk et al., 2013; Serial et al., 2021). To enable comparison across concentrations, operational pressure was normalized as specific energy input [kJ g^{-1}], which is proportional to the applied pressure divided by fibre mass. Selected CSLM images (Fig. 1) illustrate the impact of the microfluidization process on citrus fibre dispersions, with cellulosic material appearing as dark regions. CSLM images of all samples are displayed in Fig. S1 (see SI). The CSLM images reveal that the microstructure of citrus fibre dispersions is strongly affected by the processing conditions applied during microfluidization. Even at the lower limit of the specific energy input range possible for a given fibre concentration, substantial deagglomeration occurs, leading to the formation of a space-spanning network.

At low specific energy input, the network is highly heterogeneous, comprising large voids and dense fragments, which can be attributed to residual cell wall material, indicative for incomplete fibril deagglomeration. Increasing the specific energy input progressively results in a visible reduction of these dense structures and enhances deagglomeration. At the highest specific energy input applied, the CMF network seems to adopt a flocculated structure of irregular clusters giving the microstructure a more homogenous appearance (Fig. 1d). These

qualitative observations highlight the strong influence of processing conditions on microstructural organization, which is expected to govern rheological behaviour of the dispersions (Lin et al., 2015; Morales-Medina et al., 2020; Sun et al., 2020; Veen et al., 2015; You et al., 2025).

To validate these observations, quantitative metrics are needed to establish quantitative processing - microstructure relationships. A recognized method to quantify the homogeneity in CMF dispersion is the calculating the Network Homogeneity Parameter (NHP) (Veen et al., 2015). The NHP is derived from the full width half maximum (FWHM) of normalized fluorescence intensity histogram from confocal images. Higher NHP values indicates more gradual spatial intensity variations corresponding to a more evenly distribution of CMFs and CMF bundles in the dispersion. For samples with fibre concentration of 0.5 wt%, the NHP increased with specific energy input (Fig. 2a). Confocal images (Fig. 1) revealed that CMFs organize into flocs creating a microstructure of flocs and voids. The floc area fraction (Fig. 2b), assumed to be equivalent to the volume fraction (Weibel & Elias, 1967), as well as floc area (Table S2, Fig. S2) and floc diameter (Table S1, Fig. S3) were obtained through analysis of the confocal images by thresholding fibre-covered regions. For 0.5 wt% samples, the rise in NHP coincided

Fig. 1. Confocal microscopy images of 0.5 wt% citrus fibre dispersions stained with calcofluor white (scale bar: 500 μm) processed using different processing conditions. Images illustrate qualitative differences in network homogeneity and presence of cell wall fragments.

Fig. 2. a) Network Homogeneity Parameter and b) Floc volume fraction plotted against the specific energy input for samples with fibre concentration of 0.5 wt%, 1.0 wt% and 1.5 wt%.

with increased floc volume fraction (Fig. 2b), indicating that deagglomeration and redistribution of bundles produced a more space-filling network. For samples with fibre concentration of 1.0 and 1.5 wt%, tested over narrower specific energy input ranges (5–12 kJ g^{-1} and 3–8 kJ g^{-1} , respectively), both NHP and floc volume fraction showed little or no change. This likely reflects insufficient energy input to overcome crowding, rather than an absence of effect. These observations align with prior reports that microfluidization severity enhances deagglomeration primarily at dilute regimes, while microstructural changes level off in more concentrated suspensions without multiple passes (Serial et al., 2021). Overall, the specific energy input applied promotes homogenization and network expansion only when crowding does not limit effective stress transfer.

3.2. Rheology

To study the effect of the microfluidization on the viscoelastic properties of citrus fibre dispersions at varying concentrations and specific energy inputs, oscillatory rheological tests were conducted. Fig. 3 summarizes the amplitude and frequency sweep results. Both amplitude sweeps (Fig. 3a–c, e) and frequency sweeps (Fig. 3b–d, f) indicate that the dispersions exhibit gel-like behaviour under all conditions, confirming that even at the lowest specific energy input, substantial fibre deagglomeration has occurred. The amplitude sweeps characterize the onset of non-linearity and failure, critical for assessing network characteristics. When plotting parameters derived from the amplitude sweep (Fig. S2), e.g. $\tan \delta$ and yield stress σ_y it is visible that across concentrations and applied specific energy two significant trends emerge. As shown in (Fig. S2a) the critical yield strain γ_c increases with increasing specific energy input, indicating improved strain tolerance. The yield stress σ_y (Fig. S2b) is obtained by multiplying the critical yield strain by the average G' of the LVR. The yield stress σ_y peaks at moderate specific energy input for samples with fibre concentration of 0.5–1.0 wt% but dropped significantly at highest specific energy input. These trends suggest that moderate specific energy input strengthens the network, whereas very high specific energy input reduces the stress-bearing capacity. Frequency sweeps (Fig. 3b–d, f) capture the linear

viscoelastic fingerprint. Across all conditions $G' > G''$ throughout the measured angular frequency range, and both moduli followed power-law scaling $G'(\omega) \sim \omega^a$ and $G''(\omega) \sim \omega^b$ (Fig. S2d). The exponents were small ($a \approx 0.09$ – 0.15 , $b \approx 0.19$ – 0.25), confirming weak-gel behaviour with broad relaxation spectra.

While amplitude and frequency sweeps provide insights into network strength and relaxation spectra, they do not account for the time-dependent evolution of gel properties after sample loading. To address this, time sweep experiments were performed at fibre concentrations of 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5 wt% (Fig. S3). Both moduli exhibited slight temporal drift during the measurement with G' and G'' increasing marginally, consistent with the non-equilibrium relaxation of gel networks which can be attributed to artefacts from plate lowering prior to measurement (Veen et al., 2015). To ensure reproducibility, the mean values from the final 60 s of each time sweep were used for analysis.

Results from time, amplitude, and frequency sweeps indicate that the storage modulus depends on the processing conditions during the microfluidization process. To examine this relationship, the storage modulus as function of the specific energy input is shown in Fig. 4. Across all concentrations, G' exhibits a distinct non-monotonic trend with increasing specific energy input. At fibre concentrations of 0.5 wt% the storage modulus G' rises from 72.5 Pa at 4 kJ g^{-1} to a plateau of around 91.0 Pa ranging from 6 kJ g^{-1} to 20 kJ g^{-1} . Increasing the specific energy input further results in a significant decrease of the storage modulus G' to a value of 55.5 Pa at 24 kJ g^{-1} . A similar pattern is observed at 1.0 wt%, where values remain stable between 5 kJ g^{-1} and 10 kJ g^{-1} (≈ 462.0 Pa) but decrease significantly to 317.0 Pa at 12 kJ g^{-1} . For dispersions of 1.5 wt% fibre, G' plateaus between 3.3 and 6.7 kJ g^{-1} (≈ 885.0 – 925.5 Pa) and then drops to ~ 816.0 Pa at 8 kJ g^{-1} . While a downward trend is visible, the decrease is not statistically significant. These findings indicate that lower to moderate energy inputs promote the formation of a more elastic, load-bearing structure, whereas excessive energy input leads to a more compliant network. A comparable trend has been reported for ultra-high-shear treatments of cellulose fibril containing dispersions (Taheri & Samyn, 2016; Van Audenhove et al., 2022; You et al., 2025). The loss moduli follow a similar non-monotonic behaviour with specific energy input (see Fig. S4 and SI).

Fig. 3. Rheological characterization of microfluidized citrus-fibre dispersions at three concentrations (0.5 wt%, 1.0 wt%, and 1.5 wt%) and varying processing intensities. Panels (a, b) correspond to 0.5 wt%; panels (c, d) correspond to 1.0 wt%; and panels (e, f) correspond to 1.5 wt% fibre dispersions. (a, c, e): Amplitude sweeps showing storage modulus G' and loss modulus G'' as a function of shear strain. (b, d, f) Frequency sweeps showing G' and G'' versus the angular frequency. Both methods are evidencing gel-like behaviour ($G' > G''$).

3.3. Rheology – microstructure correlation

Fig. 4 highlights that, beyond a specific energy input the G' decreases consistently across all concentrations. The scaling of G' with concentration under different processing conditions is examined to elucidate the non-monotonic behaviour.

The concentration dependence of G' of gels reveals information about gel properties such as network and particle properties as well as the interactions present (Hill, 2008; Licup et al., 2015; Matsumiya et al., 2016; Song et al., 2022). Fig. 5a) presents this relationship for microfluidized citrus fibre dispersions across three different fibre concentrations and higher operational pressure may allow investigation of more concentrated dispersions. These tested fibre concentrations represent the range that could be processed reliably across the operational pressure window, as higher concentrations clogged the microfluidizer at lower pressures. The curves show a trend towards higher exponent with increasing processing pressure, highlighting the influence of treatment intensity on the concentration dependence of G' . Grouping the data by operational pressure shows that the scaling exponent increases from $n \approx 2.10$ at 500 bar to $n \approx 2.45$ at 1200 bar, with the corresponding

regression statistics reported in Table S3. This trend indicates that higher microfluidization pressure promotes a stronger concentration dependence. Future studies employing, for example, larger interaction chambers may allow investigation of more concentrated dispersions. The resulting exponents describe how G' scales with concentration under each specific operational pressure, consistent with common practice in CMF literature (Mohan et al., 2018; Naderi et al., 2014; Song et al., 2019; Veen et al., 2015). These obtained exponents for CMF-based gels derived from primary cell walls are within the wide range ($n = 2 - 5.2$) of reported experimentally obtained exponents for CMF networks from various origins (Nechyporchuk et al., 2016). These values are strongly dependent on the type of production process which influences the fibre properties as well as on the structural homogeneity (Tatsumi et al., 2002). The experimentally observed exponents indicate that citrus-derived cellulose microfibril-based networks do not exhibit the bending-dominated mechanics reported for bacterial cellulose (Veen et al., 2015) or softwood pulp derived CMF-based networks (Pääkkö et al., 2007). In contrast, the lower scaling exponents observed for microfluidized citrus fibre dispersions indicate that these systems operate in a mechanical regime dominated by entropic elasticity rather

Fig. 4. Storage modulus G' obtained from time sweep experiment (mean of last 60 s at 1 Hz, 0.1% strain) as function of specific energy input. Error bars are indicating the standard deviation.

Fig. 5. a) Storage modulus G' of the sample as a function of the fibre concentration ϕ_{fibre} . Linear fit yield the scaling exponent n , with fitted values and their errors: 500 bar: $n = 2.11 \pm 0.21$, 650 bar: $n = 2.09 \pm 0.18$, 800 bar: $n = 2.22 \pm 0.23$, 1000 bar: $n = 2.31 \pm 0.08$, 1200 bar: $n = 2.45 \pm 0.05$ b) $G'_{\text{floc}} = G'/\phi_{\text{floc}}$ as a function of microfibril-in-floc concentration $\phi_{\text{fibril in floc}} = \phi_{\text{fibre}}/\phi_{\text{floc}}$. Fit, $m = 1.6$

than rigid bending (Cao et al., 2018; Hill, 2008; MacKintosh et al., 1995). This behaviour differs markedly from bacterial cellulose, which is highly pure and exhibits very high crystallinity, resulting in an exceptionally high Young's modulus that governs fibril rigidity. By comparison, cellulose from primary cell walls generally shows lower crystallinity, which reduces stiffness as the Young's modulus decreases. Additionally, citrus fibre contains soluble biopolymers such as pectin and hemicellulose, which may influence fibril-fibril interactions and contribute to the observed differences in network mechanics (Agoda-Tandjawa et al., 2012). The analysis is based on three different

fibre concentrations, as this range corresponds to the concentrations that can be reliably processed across the required pressure window and therefore captures the relevant scaling behaviour accessible for this system.

The observation that the experimental obtained power-law scaling of the bulk storage modulus as a function of the bulk fibre concentration varies with the operational pressure applied during the microfluidization process indicates that bulk scaling mixes the intrinsic stiffness of the fibrils and the changes in the network structure caused by varying the processing parameter. As visible in confocal images (Fig. 1),

the microfluidization process reorganizes the CMF-based particles into fibre-rich regions (flocs), which are separated by voids. This heterogeneous microstructure makes interpretation of the bulk network behaviour difficult. To determine the viscoelasticity of the distinct network of fibres, the floc modulus (G'_{floc}) using the Reuss-Voigt-Hill averaging scheme (Chatterjee, 2011; Reuss, 1929; Voigt, 1889).

Rheological measurements of the continuous phase (Fig. S6) show that the supernatant storage modulus remains small across all specific energy inputs tested, with values of the order of 10^{-3} - 10^{-1} Pa. These values are several orders of magnitude lower than the bulk storage modulus (55.4-94.0 Pa), confirming that the continuous phase does not contribute measurably to the load-bearing behaviour of the dispersion. This conclusion is further supported by literature on citrus pectin, which shows that even at comparatively high concentrations (~2-4 wt%), pectin dispersions remain viscous-dominated with low elastic moduli (Asimakopoulou et al., 2024), far below the moduli of the bulk samples studied. Moreover, pectin is known to undergo depolymerization during high-pressure homogenization and microfluidization, reducing molecular weight and further suppressing its ability to form elastic structures (Chen et al., 2012).

The void regions can therefore be treated as mechanically non-load bearing ($G'_{void} \approx 0$). Under this assumption, the RVH model reduces to a simple relation between the bulk modulus and the floc modulus $G' = \phi_{floc} G'_{floc}$, enabling direct estimation of the viscoelastic properties of the flocs.

Given that voids are considered cellulose fibre-free regions all fibrils are localized within the flocs. Accounting for the concentration of fibrils inside the flocs $\phi_{fibril\ in\ floc} = \phi_{fibre}/\phi_{floc}$, a distinct power-law behaviour $G'_{floc} = k * \phi_{fibril\ in\ floc}^m$, with the pre-factor k representing the elasticity of the material backbone, is observed. Fig. 5b) shows the power-law for samples treated at various specific energy inputs. The resulting exponent $m = 1.6$ is markedly lower than the exponents observed for the bulk network. Crucially, unlike the exponent n obtained from bulk scaling, the intra-floc exponent m remains constant across all tested operational pressures. Although changes within the flocs may occur at processing conditions beyond the experimentally accessible range, the invariance of m within this window indicates that specific energy input primarily reorganizes the spatial arrangement of flocs rather than altering their internal mechanics. Taken together, these findings suggest that the microfluidization conditions used here predominantly influence floc connectivity at the mesoscale, while the local fibril-level structure inside flocs remains largely unaffected.

To assess how the specific energy input dictates the microstructural organization, and thereby the measured bulk storage modulus G' , we define an intrinsic scaling factor. The factor is derived from the assumption that the bulk storage modulus equals the storage modulus of the floc weighted by the floc volume fraction (ϕ_{floc}), $G'_{floc} = G'/\phi_{floc}$ as described by the Reuss-Voigt-Hill model (Chatterjee, 2011; Hill, 1952). Within each floc, the storage modulus is (G'_{floc}) scales with the microfibril concentration inside that floc $\phi_{fibril-in-floc}$, following a power-law with exponent m (Fig. 5b): $G'_{floc} = \phi_{fibril-in-floc}^m$. Mass conservation links the intra-floc and bulk fibre concentration via $\phi_{fibril\ in\ floc} = \phi_{fibre}/\phi_{floc}$. Combining these relations, we can express the storage modulus as a function of the volume fraction of flocs, ϕ_{floc} , and the bulk fibre concentration ϕ_{bulk} :

$$G' = k \phi_{floc} \left(\frac{\phi_{fibre}}{\phi_{floc}} \right)^m \quad (5)$$

which rearranges to:

$$\frac{G'}{\phi_{fibre}^m} = k \phi_{floc}^{1-m} \quad (6)$$

Here, k captures intrinsic material properties (i.e. crystallinity) and microfibril geometry. For athermal microfibrils dispersions, k typically

scales with the microfibril Young's modulus and aspect ratio, following a power law. Tatsumi et al. reported a scaling of k with the square of the aspect ratio for dispersions of cellulose microfibrils (Tatsumi et al., 2002). Plotting the scaled modulus G'/ϕ_{fibre}^m against the specific input energy input collapses data across all fibre concentrations onto a single master curve (Fig. 6), confirming that the specific energy governs the effective floc volume fraction ϕ_{floc}^{1-m} and the intrinsic material properties (k) resulting in variation in bulk modulus G' . The collapsed curve indicates a gradual transition in behaviour with increasing specific energy input, with a gradual change occurring around a threshold point $E_c \approx 7.5 \text{ kJ g}^{-1}$. This value can serve as a convenient phenomenological marker highlighting where the dominant response begins to shift under the specific combination of fibre type, concentration, and microfluidization conditions used. Since the specific energy reflects the macroscopic work applied to the dispersion, the specific energy input of $E_c \approx 7.5 \text{ kJ g}^{-1}$ can be used to denote an approximate point along a continuous evolution between the two observed regimes.

At low specific energy inputs (specific energy input $< E_c$), the scaled modulus increases slightly with specific energy input. CSLM images (Fig. 2b) reveal a decreasing trend in ϕ_{floc} , indicating denser flocs with higher intra-floc fibre concentration $\phi_{fibril\ in\ floc}$. This densification likely enhances connectivity and load-bearing capacity, explaining the modest increase in scaled modulus.

Beyond E_c , the trend reverses: G'/ϕ_{fibre}^m decreases as specific energy input increases. Initially, this correlates with a sharp increase in ϕ_{floc} (Fig. 2b), which reduces intra-floc fibre concentration. However, at the highest energies (20-24 kJ g^{-1}), ϕ_{floc} decreases again (Fig. 2b), yet the scaled modulus G'/ϕ_{fibre}^m continues to drop. This indicates that floc volume fraction alone cannot explain the trend and suggests that additional fibril-level mechanisms may begin to contribute. For this, two possible explanations may also play a role. First, employing high processing intensities during ultra-high shear processing is known to reduce crystallinity of cellulose fibres by disrupting hydrogen bonding and this effect is often more pronounced when smaller interaction chambers, such as the 87 μm chamber used in our work, are applied. (Fatah et al., 2014; Iwamoto et al., 2007; Li et al., 2019; Taheri & Samyn, 2016). Lower crystallinity would decrease the microfibril's Young's modulus (Guo et al., 2016), reducing the pre-factor k and thus G'/ϕ_{fibre}^m . Second, excessive energy input during ultra-high shear processing of cellulose fibres could result in shortening of them, lowering their aspect ratio (You et al., 2025). Since k scales strongly with the aspect ratio, this shortening would further reduce the scaled modulus. Overall, we hypothesise that an interplay of three effects (increase in ϕ_{floc} , decrease in crystallinity and decrease in aspect ratio) are likely to contribute to the observed decreasing behaviour of G'/ϕ_{fibre}^m with specific energy input.

This analysis establishes a direct processing-structure-property link: specific energy controls floc network architecture and intrinsic microfibril properties, which together govern the mechanics of the microfluidized citrus fibre dispersions. Future work should quantify changes in k and floc structure under varying energy inputs and compare different processing methods to build a comprehensive understanding.

4. Conclusions

In this study, the specific energy input during microfluidization functions as a parameter governing change in microstructure and rheology and is employed to establish a quantitative link between processing intensity, microstructure and mechanical response in citrus-fibre dispersions. Increasing specific energy input modulates the microstructure of the cellulose microfibril present in the citrus fibre, as quantified through descriptors such as floc volume fraction and network homogeneity. These microstructural changes affect the elasticity of the network, with moderate energy inputs strengthen network elasticity and excessive inputs reduce structural integrity.

Fig. 6. Scaled storage modulus $G' / \phi_{\text{fibre}}^m$ plotted as a function of specific energy input.

Scaling analysis revealed that the concentration dependence of the bulk storage modulus is influenced by processing history, with exponents varying between $n \approx 2.1$ – 2.5 . In contrast, intra-floc scaling yielded a constant exponent $m \approx 1.6$, suggesting that specific energy input reorganizes floc connectivity rather than altering local microfibril mechanics. Normalizing G' by this intrinsic exponent collapses the data onto a single master curve governed by specific energy input, revealing two regimes: (i) below $\sim 7.5 \text{ kJ g}^{-1}$, elasticity increases due to floc densification; (ii) above this threshold, elasticity declines, likely reflecting a combination of increased floc volume fraction and hypothesised fibril-level changes such as reduced crystallinity or lower aspect ratio.

While the decline in elasticity at higher energy inputs is consistent with these interpretations, the contributions of crystallinity and fibril length therefore remain inferred. Citrus fibre inherently is a multi-component system, and some degree of pectin solubilization or redistribution under high shear may influence fibre-matrix interactions. However, rheological measurements show that the elasticity of the continuous phase of microfluidized citrus fibre dispersions is low and assumed to be negligible. A more comprehensive picture of how specific energy input during microfluidization influences microstructure and rheology of dispersions of citrus fibre would emerge from quantifying fibril-level properties, quantifying pectin release and investigate its contribution to the cellulose microfibril network, widening the processing window by investigating multiple microfluidization passes, and incorporating 3D network characterisation, thereby deepening insight into the governing processing-structure-property relationships.

Overall, the findings provide a coherent mechanistic framework for tailoring CMF-based networks through controlled microfluidization and support the rational design of clean-label food gels and texture modifiers.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Lennard Schulte: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Krassimir P. Velikov:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work the authors used Microsoft Copilot in order to enhance readability. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2026.112541>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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